

Intervention on the mental health of health workers during the first 18 months of the pandemic of COVID-19

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has severely impacted the mental health of populations worldwide, with healthcare workers being particularly vulnerable. They have witnessed the rising number of deaths among patients and colleagues, all while fearing infection and the possibility of transmitting the virus to their loved ones. In addition, healthcare workers have experienced increased responsibilities and extended working hours (Albott et al., 2020). Some have even been subjected to violence and discrimination. In response, various health organizations have proposed psychological strategies to support the mental well-being of healthcare workers and have published treatment protocols. However, due to the ongoing nature of the pandemic, only short-term treatment effects have been studied so far.

Electronic health interventions (eHealth interventions) have proven beneficial in preventing health problems and promoting resilience across different populations (Stratton et al., 2017). These interventions are particularly relevant during the COVID-19 pandemic, where social distancing remains crucial to preventing the spread of the virus.

As part of the HEROES-Colombia study we are implementing, we aim to design an eHealth intervention that is both feasible and acceptable to the healthcare worker community. The first step in this process involves reviewing the literature on treatments that have already

been developed. Our research question is: What are the key topics and strategies to consider in designing an effective eHealth intervention for addressing healthcare workers' mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Methods

We conducted a systematic literature review of articles published from December 2019 to June 2021 in the databases Pubmed, PsycINFO, EMBASE, and SciELO. In addition, we reviewed some documents on eHealth intervention by renowned health organizations or academic institutions. The search terms in English and Spanish were related to 1) Mental Health problems, 2) Intervention, 3) Health workers, and 4) COVID-19 pandemic.

We included studies with qualitative and quantitative methodology describing treatment approaches used with health workers during the pandemic and health communications, written in English or Spanish. We excluded articles not published in peer-reviewed journals or not sponsored by renowned health organizations. In addition, we excluded other grey literature, such as dissertations and studies focused only on pharmacological interventions. Based on the PICO Tool:

For Quantitative Studies

POPULATION: Health workers

INTERVENTION: Virtual or in-person therapies that include at least a component of prevention or treatment of mental health problems or promotion of resilience.

COMPARISON: Depending on the study type, between treatment groups and standard of care

OUTCOME: Short- and long-term effects in the reduction of anxiety or depression

For qualitative articles and documents:

POPULATION OR PROBLEM: Health Problems in Health workers (as previously defined) during the pandemic of COVID-19

INTEREST: Experiences of treatment or intervention

CONTEXT: Virtual and in-person environment

After removing duplicates, two independent reviewers selected the papers. We discarded papers as follows: title, abstract, and full text using Covidence software. Selected papers that met the eligibility criteria were stored in Endnote. The selected articles were organized considering: 1) Title 2) Organization 3) Type of document (journal paper, health report) 4) Country and city 5) Sample characteristics or target population 6) Target mental health problems 7) Characteristics of the intervention, description of strategies 8) Main findings or conclusions.

Results

The initial search in the databases led to 247 records, and two additional documents were obtained from known health organizations. After a title and abstract screening and a full-text review, we selected seventeen articles to extract.

Figure 1. Article selection process

General Characteristics of the Studies

Of the seventeen studies included, six proposed an intervention (Albott et al., 2020; Benhamou & Piedra, 2020; Bueno Ferrán & Barrientos-Trigo, 2021; Chandra & Vanjare, 2020; Gupta & Sahoo, 2020; Karnatovskaia et al., 2020), nine implemented or were in the process of implementing an intervention (Dehkordi et al., 2020; Dincer & Inangil, 2021; Giordano et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Muñoz-Martínez et al., 2021; Tarquinio et al., 2020; Vajpeyee et al., 2021; Viswanathan et al., 2020; Weiner et al., 2020), and two (Becker, 2021; Muller et al., 2020) were literature reviews on interventions targeting the mental health of healthcare workers during COVID-19. These reviews identified seven additional studies on implemented interventions. One of the reviews identified six studies (Cao et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Chung & Yeung, 2020; Hong et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2020; Schulte et al., 2020) that did not appear in our database search. The other review was more specific to sleep management and identified two studies on interventions, one of which did not appear in our search.

The countries of the implemented interventions (including those identified in the literature reviews) were distributed as follows: Asian countries (8), European countries (4), North American countries (3), and South American countries (1).

All proposed interventions could be implemented virtually. In addition, three of the already implemented interventions were either in-person or used a mixed virtual and in-person strategy but could also be fully virtual.

Most of the implemented interventions focused on individual strategies without making institutional changes, except for two ongoing support groups (Dehkordi et al., 2020; Viswanathan et al., 2020) and two studies identified by Muller et al. (2021), which involved organizational adjustments. All of the interventions included nurses, or worked exclusively with frontline nurses.

Furthermore, all completed studies reported a significant reduction in mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and stress, as well as a significant increase in resilience or other adaptive behaviors after the intervention. The interventions were also well-accepted by participants.

Characteristics of the Interventions

The proposed and implemented interventions were equally derived from structured therapeutic approaches and other techniques. Structured therapeutic approaches such as Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT; Benhamou & Piedra, 2020; Weiner et al., 2020), Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT; Muñoz-Martínez et al., 2021), Battle Buddies (Albott et al., 2020), support groups (Dehkordi et al., 2020; Viswanathan et al., 2020), diaphragmatic

breathing (Liu et al., 2021), and Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR; Tarquinio et al., 2020) were proposed. Other interventions/techniques included music therapy (Giordano et al., 2020; Vajpeyee et al., 2021), yoga (Vajpeyee et al., 2021; Lai et al., 2020), mindfulness (Muñoz-Martínez et al., 2021; Weiner et al., 2020), and the Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT; Dincer & Inangil, 2021).

Common strategies included effective communication, body awareness/meditation, evaluating stress-inducing situations, validating emotions, training in coping strategies, reducing information overload, and promoting resilience and optimism.

The most commonly assessed outcomes were stress, insomnia, depression, and anxiety (with the State Anxiety Scale being the most frequently used), as these are the most common mental health problems among healthcare workers and the general population globally.

Regarding the length of the nine implemented interventions reviewed in detail (see Table 3), two interventions consisted of only one session (Dincer & Inangil, 2021; Tarquinio et al., 2020), while the other seven involved at least six sessions lasting two weeks to a month.

Three studies consisted of initial training followed by repetition for a specified period (Giordano et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Tarquinio et al., 2020). Two studies, one based on ACT FACE COVID (first proposed by Harris, 2020; Muñoz-Martínez et al., 2021) and one on CBT (Weiner et al., 2020), covered various topics and were the most comprehensive, with suggested activities and topics for each session. Only two studies described ongoing interventions (Dehkordi et al., 2020; Viswanathan et al., 2020).

Among the proposed interventions (see Table 1), the descriptions of the Battle Buddies (Albott et al., 2020) and APPLE (Karnatovskaia et al., 2020) techniques were the most detailed in terms of topics and intervention strategies.

Table 1. Proposed interventions

Authors	Main reason for inclusión	Target population	Main topics	Strategies
1. Albott, Wozniak, et al. (2020)(1)	Full description of the "Battle Buddies" intervention in the context of COVID-19	Healthcare workers	Coping and resilience Enhancing social connection Identify and support at-risk individuals	Along with a Battle Buddy: Anticipate stressors Plan how to cope with stressors Deter, seek help from a mental health professional
2. Benhamou and Piedra (2020)(3)	Description of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) intervention strategies	Essential healthcare workers	CBT strategies	Meeting basic needs Empathic listening and validation Values clarification Interpersonal effectiveness Self-monitoring and behavioral activation Limiting intake of information
3. Bueno and Barrientos (2021)(4)	Description of intervention strategies in nurses	Nurses and other healthcare professionals	Reduce emotional impact	Physical activity Diaphragmatic breathing Disconnect Strengthen support Ask for professional help
4. Chandra & Vanjare (2020)(5)	Conducted a review of the literature to identify main problems and make suggestions	Healthcare workers in developing countries	Optimism Psychological Support Communication	Decrease stress in the workplace Assist prosperity of medical staff Psychological support facilities
5. Gupta & Sahoo (2020)(6)	Conducted a review of the literature to identify main problems to make suggestions	Healthcare workers in the Indian context	Improving effective communication	Effective communication Tangible support from the administration Mental health problem screening and facilities Making isolation less restrictive Ensuring interpersonal communication through the various digital platforms Proactively curtail misinformation

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Authors	Main reason for inclusión	Target population	Main topics	Strategies
6. Karnatovskaia, Johnson, et al. (2020)(7)	A thorough description of intervention strategies	Healthcare workers	Resilience Positive mindset Be grateful and acknowledge flaws Have mindful patient interactions	Among others, suggested strategies were: Breathing techniques Meditate Practice self-care APPLE technique (acknowledge, pause, pull-back, explore) Reflect Have a positive self-image Say "thank you" and "sorry."

Table 2. Literature reviews

Author(s)	Included studies	City and country of included studies	Objectives	Topics	Strategies
Becker (2021)(17)	Review of 53 studies, only 2 proposed for frontline workers to reduce insomnia: The study by Weiner et al. (2020) (described in Table 3) and one by Lai, lonson, et al.(2020)(25)	London, Canada	To reduce poor sleep in health workers	Yoga	Three-hour breathing training and/or mind-body interventions
Muller, Hafstad, et al. (2020)(18)	Included 59 studies. Identified six studies on interventions Cao et al.(2020)(19), Schulte et al. (2020)(24), Jiang et al. (2020)(23), Chen et al. (2020)(20), Hong et al. (2021 newest version)(22), Chung and Jeung (2020)(21)	Five cities in China, one in New York, USA	Improve mental health of health workers	Two involved observational adjustments One facilitated team/collegial support Five addressed individual complaints or strategies.	Rest spaces Shortened shifts Available hotline Support of the labor union Training on how to address patient distress Support calls

Table 3. Mental health interventions implemented

Authors	City and Country	Sample	Type of intervention	Objective	Strategies	Acceptability/ Effectiveness
1. Dehkordi, Sakhi, et al. (2020)(8)	Tehran, Iran	10 healthcare workers (physicians and nurses)	E-health Balint groups. 6 to 8 1-hour sessions, 2-3 times per week	To reduce anxiety and increase resilience	Find joint solutions to problems faced with patients and psychological stressors	Comparing pre-post scores on the Corona Disease Anxiety Scale (CDAS) and Connor–Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC), at $p < 0.01$, there was significant decrease in anxiety scores and significant increase in resilience scores
2. Dincer & Inangbil (2021)(9)	Istanbul, Turkey	72 nurses. 35 in the intervention and 37 in the control group	E-health (guided online). One Emotional Freedom Technique session	To reduce stress, anxiety and burnout levels in nurses	Evoke an anxiety-inducing issue Do acupressure in some specific points Repeat positive affirmations Follow a sequence of specific movements	Comparing the SUD, the SAS and the Burnout scale scores in the treatment and control groups, there was a significantly greater decrease at $p < 0.01$ in the mean scores of stress anxiety and burnout in the intervention group
3. Giordano, Scarlata, et al. (2020)(10)	Bari, Italy	34 clinical staff nurses/doctors	Was done in person, but could also be e-health. Participants were asked to listen to selected and customized playlists daily for two weeks	To reduce stress and improve well-being	Playlists to improve: Breathing, energy and serenity	Comparing the MTC-Q1 pre-post scores, there was a significant improvement at $p < 0.05$ in the mean scores of breathing, energy and serenity
4. Liu, Jiang, et al. (2021)(11)	Wuhan, China	151 nurses	E-health. With screening, information, audio recordings, and videos to practice at least once per day for a month	To improve sleep quality in frontline nurses	Diaphragmatic relaxation training	Comparing the PSQI and the SAS pre-post scores, there was a significant ($p < 0.01$) improvement in the mean scores of sleep quality and decreased mean scores of anxiety.
5. Muñoz-Martínez, Otto-Scheiber, et al. (2021)(12)	Bogotá, Colombia	12 healthcare workers	E-health. 10 videos and audios, infographics, and cartoons for complementary activities and homework	To assess acceptability and Scalability of the FACE COVID intervention (Harris, 2020)	F: Focus on what is in your control A: Acknowledge thoughts and feelings C: Come back into your body E: Focus your attention on the world around you and on what	FACE COVID is a scalable and acceptable intervention based on participant and expert assessment (3.3/4). The Intervention is currently being implemented to a larger sample

Table 3. Mental health interventions implemented

Authors	City and Country	Sample	Type of intervention	Objective	Strategies	Acceptability/ Effectiveness
			assignments, based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT)		you do C: Clarify your values O: Choose to act according to your values V: Living with disposition to your experience I: Identify resources D: Physical, not emotional distancing	
6. Tarquinio, Brennstuhl, et al. (2020)(13)	Metz, France	17 healthcare workers	E-health.Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR) training and implementation lasting over 2 hours	To investigate the satisfaction and effectiveness of the URG-EMDR protocol in the treatment of anxiety, depression and perceived disturbance	Consider history Psychoeducation and stabilization Rewinding to episodes and create fragments Desensitization	Comparing the HAD and the SUD pre-post scores, there was a significant ($p<0.05$) decrease mean scores of anxiety, depression and perceived disturbance 24 hours and 1 week after intervention. Analyses showed satisfaction with the intervention
7. Vajpejee, Tiwari, et al. (2021)(14)	Rajasthan, India	209 healthcare workers randomized into intervention and control groups	Mix of in-person and e-health intervention. Daily 30-minute sessions of yoga and music therapy for one month	To assess impact of yoga and music intervention on anxiety, stress and depression	Training in yoga poses and personalized playlists by music therapists	Significantly ($p<0.01$) greater decrease of anxiety, depression and stress in the intervention vs the control group

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Authors	City and Country	Sample	Type of intervention	Objective	Strategies	Acceptability/ Effectiveness
8. Viswanathan, Myers, and Fanous (2020)(15)	New York, USA	130 participants in group sessions 57 participants in individual sessions	E-health. Weekly group sessions of 40 minutes. Individual sessions as needed	To develop support systems to cope with stress	Strategies related to the topics: Acceptance by group Acceptance of situation Altruism Catharsis Consensual validation Guidance Insight Instillation of hope Interpersonal learning Peer support	Not measured
9. Weiner, Berna, et al. (2020)(16)	Eastern Region, France	120 participants expected	E-health. Seven 20-minute sessions of online CBT over eight weeks	To investigate the efficacy and the acceptability of a 7-session internet-based CBT program	Strategies related to the topics: Psychological mechanisms of stress Useful behaviors during stressful situations Mindfulness Resilience Valued actions Self-compassion and self-care Self-compassion and emotion regulation	In progress

Discussion

The numerous mental health risks faced by healthcare workers worldwide are a significant concern, as demonstrated by the growing interest in providing acceptable, feasible, and effective interventions to reduce anxiety, depression, and stress while improving resilience.

However, many proposed interventions focus on strategies that are seldom implemented by healthcare services, such as organizational adjustments, ongoing treatment, support groups, and changes in shifts and responsibilities. Despite their potential long-term benefits, these organizational adjustments are challenging to implement due to their high initial financial costs.

More intervention efforts are underway but not yet published, such as the ACT FACE COVID study. Additionally, many interventions may never be published because they are not considered innovative or are implemented in healthcare institutions that rarely focus on research. Published or not, all efforts made by healthcare institutions to improve the mental health of their workers are beneficial, but they may involve high costs and face challenges related to acceptability and feasibility among healthcare workers, which could reduce their overall effectiveness.

Our findings in this systematic literature review highlight the primary targets, outcomes, and most acceptable and feasible strategies to consider when creating a cost-effective intervention that can be implemented on an ongoing basis in hospitals in Colombia and similar contexts.

First, all studies described e-health interventions or interventions that could be adapted to an e-health format. This is a crucial finding for the feasibility and acceptability of mental health interventions among healthcare workers, particularly given the need for social distancing to prevent contagion and the flexibility of scheduling. E-health interventions also offer the advantage of anonymity for workers who may prefer not to discuss their concerns with colleagues.

Based on the duration and number of sessions in the reviewed interventions, an acceptable and feasible e-health intervention should include at least seven sessions, each lasting less than an hour. This structure allows participants to experience positive effects, reinforce learned strategies, and avoid feeling overwhelmed, making it easier to complete than interventions with longer sessions.

We found that crisis management skills, such as resilience, are rarely evaluated before implementing interventions for healthcare workers. Instead, the focus tends to be on screening for mental health problems like anxiety and depression. Therefore, we suggest that before implementing an intervention, healthcare workers' crisis management skills should be assessed to emphasize that the goal is not only to reduce mental health issues but also to enhance skills for managing future challenges.

It is important to note that although most interventions followed a structured approach, they all incorporated changes when something was not working and maintained open communication with participants. This likely increased the acceptability of the interventions among healthcare workers. We recommend always providing space for questions and

suggestions in future interventions. Additionally, to improve communication, each session should begin with a clear description of its objectives, expected duration, and planned activities.

We propose focusing on topics identified in our findings: understanding stress mechanisms, recognizing individual skills and needs, coping with stressful situations, practicing self-compassion and self-care, improving sleep hygiene, relaxation techniques, managing work-life relationships, regulating emotions, and building resilience. These topics were selected based on literature searches and the reported needs of healthcare workers.

We also propose including the topic of stigma, which was not addressed in the selected studies. Stigma disproportionately affects doctors and those in higher positions within healthcare organizations, potentially preventing them from seeking treatment or adhering to interventions.

Based on the findings of this literature review, strategies that were effective in addressing mental health issues before the pandemic have also been effective and accepted by healthcare workers during COVID-19. Commonly used strategies include providing information, self-assessment and self-monitoring of behaviors, meditation techniques, mindfulness, cognitive defusion, modeling and training in coping and self-care skills, physical activity to improve sleep quality, yoga, and music therapy. These strategies are grounded in well-established therapeutic approaches such as CBT and ACT, as well as alternative therapies like yoga and music therapy. Therefore, when designing an intervention for healthcare workers in

Colombia and similar contexts, we recommend considering both conventional and alternative strategies, provided the objectives and expectations are clearly defined from the outset.

In summary, this systematic review serves as a foundational framework for designing an e-health intervention aimed at improving the mental health of healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic, ensuring that it is viable and accepted in Colombia and similar settings.

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